

VISUAL WORKFLOWS FOR DESIGN PROJECT KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the findings of research into a digital learning knowledge management tool that uses an interactive surface to manipulate a design project in multiple stages. The research aim was to understand how designers might replace the traditional model of one device per person and use digital space as an alternative for analyzing data collaboratively. The research involved using one device for multiple users, including multi-gesture and navigability options to organize data and learning that were generated by team dynamics. Two different tests were implemented: a concept test about the general idea and a usability test with different groups of designers, to examine team dynamics. In the discussion section we consider how participants had problems recognizing a single device as appropriate for use in group activities, how the focus of attention in the interactive table took away some of the gestures and non-verbal communication that are common in team dynamics, how the novelty of the device created an initial exploration that was perceived as a game and how using an interactive technology as a tool created different levels of learning that affect the emotional response of participants. The paper concludes with recommendations about future implementations and some interesting patterns characterizing the use of the multi-touch gesture screen, such as the use of digital space as a way to control activities and the deliberate control of data as a way to impose a leadership.

KEYWORDS: *Collaborative design; communication; computer supported design; decision making; design activity.*

INTRODUCTION

Although there are a variety of project management tools available, designers are notorious for their unwillingness to employ them in anything but the most rudimentary fashion (e.g. Bernardes forthcoming). One of the barriers to adoption is the essential non-linearity of the design process, where the iterative return to previous stages of the project is typical rather than exceptional. In this study, we created a prototype for knowledge management in design projects, based on the foursquare model of research, analysis, synthesis and implementation, superimposed on an X-axis running from understanding the paper layout to making, and a Y-axis running from the real to the abstract (Figure 1). Recognizing that each of these phases needs to be ready at hand, our touch surface prototype keeps a dynamic menu object constantly available, allowing designers occupying any position on the table to shift the display quickly from the collection of raw data, to organize it by using analysis and labeling and to achieve a final synthesis and labeling protocol. We also provide a simple mechanism for generating linear presentation materials for use outside the design team proper. The design of the

prototype was informed by interviews with seven design managers at five different firms. Our user study of the prototype involved two different tests, a usability test of the working prototype with 12 design students and a concept test with a "Wizard of Oz" prototype, involving five design managers

Figure 1. The underlying model for our design management prototype. Diagram by Kim Erwin.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In product development, there are two types of project management styles: emergent and planned [4]. The planned project management style is suited to clearly defined problems, where managers provide discipline, set direction, and optimize for efficiency. The former, emergent, style is better suited to ambiguous problems, where managers enable their subordinates to be creative and flexible and to improvise solutions. According to Lewis, managers do not solely practice one style, but rather combine and alternate between both methods. While the planned management style relies heavily on time as a key measure, the emergent style heavily relies on knowledge and learning through iterations [3]. Currently, there are many similar market-available tools to facilitate the planned management style, while there are few to facilitate emergent methods. As a result, our team focused on developing tools for activities that occur in emergent product development, particularly with regards to knowledge sharing.

According to Wang [6], successful knowledge systems are heavily influenced by:

- Easy and effective methods for adding data and searching categories and indexes;
- Preferences for autocratic or consultative management styles; and
- The complexity level of the project.

Furthermore, Wang [6] suggests that there are two types of communication styles. The first involves linear, formal and vertical sharing (such as PowerPoint presentations) and the second involves informal, egalitarian sharing (such as conversations and discussions). Because both styles of communication are present within an organization, the tool that our team developed was required to support both styles and help users capture and transfer knowledge easily between the two styles and their associated contexts.

Additionally, according to Zigurs [8], technology, while good at communication, process-setting and information handling, is not adaptable to support teams in the midst of reframing and restructuring. The project management prototype developed by the team will specifically look at this assertion, as it is designed to facilitate and capture new connections between data, while still providing access to old connections developed in other stages.

Specifically, the team investigated group dynamics and leadership around control of the Multitaction table, which is designed for multiple, simultaneous users. As Yuill and Rogers [7] and Hesselmann et al. [2] contest, a number of social and cultural barriers exist that may prevent multiple users from touching the table simultaneously. Many current devices are designed for individual and single user input. In addition, social norms may also dictate who touches the table at a given time – e.g. where the leader of the group “controls the screen”. Visual limitations (i.e., the ability to see a graphic from one’s vantage point) and the physical reach of objects may also influence who touches the table at the appropriate moment.

Finally, the team also looked at the translation of natural gestures used for handling and sorting images in the physical world to the constraints of the digital touch surface. Terrenghi [5] compares the manipulation-related affordances of physical media and interactive surfaces. Similarly, the team explored the gestures and screenflows involved in sorting and surveying images, forming collections, and hiding inessential or irrelevant information.

METHODS

For the purposes of the study, the team focused particularly on individuals involved in “design thinking” who use various research and creative methods and need to collect, organize and share out information in a collaborative setting with others. The team also felt that design consultancies with multiple disciplines and competencies were solidly extreme users who typically work with a variety of visual and physical content, generated from a wide range of tools (sketches, the Adobe Creative suite, video, physical prototypes, etc.).

During the collaborative design process, team members need to create a fundamental shared understanding of design content and process as well as to capture (or document when needed) information that allows others to understand, communicate, replicate or redesign the final output [1].

While there are digital tools that exist for designers to create by themselves, few exist to help them create simultaneously in a collaborative experience. Instead, from our observations and from ethnographic interviews, design teams still resort to physical displays in their environments because these allow all members to contribute, and to move information readily.

INITIAL RESEARCH

The team interviewed designers and project managers from different firms, ranging from small to large and from consultancies to Fortune 500 companies – over a range of competencies from CPG to technology.

Findings

We began with the hypothesis that organizations struggle with project management and that current tools were inadequate to the task. However, after interviewing participants, the team realized that organizations didn’t struggle with project management because tools such as the Gantt chart have made it easy to set deadlines and show the time-based relationships between departments. Managers can easily see whether a project is off-track by comparing current team activity with the planned schedule.

However, in companies where generated knowledge and insight are the key measures of success (in fields such as emerging technologies and development work), a Gantt chart is not an effective management tool for understanding if a project is

“on track” or generating expected value. It is in this scenario that organizations and teams struggle to report project value, because they find it hard to communicate their work within the teams themselves and to key stakeholders.

One participant described the hiring of specialized staff (known as “research public relations”) to highlight key technological contributions to external partners and lobby for further research investment. This allows technologists in the R&D division to focus on their research problems and not on communicating the value and progress of their work.

The team found that design managers and consultants particularly struggle with this problem in their role as client liaisons. Specifically, designers rely on the vertical space and the environment around them to manage, organize and share their knowledge internally.

- In contrast to digital tools, where teams rely on one person to move data in a turn-like fashion, posting to vertical surfaces is democratic: everyone is allowed to contribute and rearrange data.
- Vertical space also passively communicates the team’s progress to outside participants. Picture-filled boards communicate that the team has just completed the research phase while boards filled with page layouts denote a team that is preparing documents or presentations.

While teams opt to use their physical space to manage their data they struggle with transferring all of their digital data to the physical world. This means tediously printing out hundreds of research photographs and creating extensive paper snippets of interview transcripts or secondary research papers.

Similarly, when designers need to communicate their final work, they must convert all of those physical assets back to a digital format, usually a PowerPoint or PDF deck for their client, so the information can travel throughout the client organization. While the data might be stored in a shared location on a server or cloud service, designers still need to find all of the digital assets for their physical counterparts.

Even with walls or boards covered with data and recorded by photographs, there is never enough space for everything and designers must rely on their own documentation habits to remember design decisions. Their photographs of data clusters aren’t searchable or easily retrievable, allowing to track decisions they’ve made or patterns they’ve seen.

Additionally, at the end of the project, it is common for companies to save their digital files, but only a few store the physical information in archive systems that retain a mix of digital and tangible information. In trying to access the archives the experience is chaotic, and retrieving a specific stage of the project requires all the data to be scanned. In the same way, it is common to find information that is out of context as the learning experience of the original design team is absent.

CONCEPT TEST PROTOTYPE

In response to the feedback of our interviewees, we designed a tool that was intended to manage this information digitally through a unique use of environment, space and collaboration. Using these design principles, the team developed a concept prototype of a digital knowledge management tool

Figure 2: Concept, “Wizard of Oz” Prototype. Screen 1 = User setup. Screen 2 = Loading data. Screen 3 = Creating clusters. Screen 4 =Presentation layout display mode.

in Apple Keynote for the multi-touch Multitaction table in order to help design managers organize and share their data. Similarly to the current vertical space environment, the tool is designed to be orthogonally democratic. Most functions (with the exception of the presentation function) are designed to be executed by any team member at any edge of the table surface, regardless of another team member's actions (i.e., the table is designed to be always in "multiplayer mode").

After creating a project using the table's interface, and assigning team members to the project, users can select data snippets, such as image files, video clips and text, to be loaded onto the table's surface. Upon data selection, the materials populate the table's surface in a slow, randomized display in different orientations. Items can be rotated, moved and zoomed in an effort to organize them into named sets, or "clusters". Clusters can be named, marked as important, organized temporarily in a grid structure, and copied. Important contextual information, or "insights", about the clusters can be documented via text input and attached to the cluster as an additional data snippet.

As users enter new stages of the design process they can create duplicates of the same information for reworking or the information can be progressively reduced to the most important pieces for analysis. In each stage, the same clustering actions serve as the central form of interaction with the table. When users want to communicate their work, they can switch to a visualization mode that organizes all of the data snippets, clusters and insights in a simple grid structure according to time. At any point, users can switch between stages and visualizations, and the table display is captured using auto-save functions.

User Research

We investigated three key areas with the prototype, and sought to:

1. Understand how users learn new gestures that are beyond currently accepted digital norms (swiping, double tapping, pinching, or expanding)
2. Understand the role of team dynamics and how the table can facilitate or hinder participation by team members.
3. Understand the acceptance and desirability of such a tool for the industry.

The first two questions are related to specific activities and behaviors concerning the physical prototype and the implementation of the concept in a multi-touch, collaborative environment. The third area is related to the application of the concept in the design workflow. We therefore developed two different tests. The first was a concept test covering all of the stages of the design process with a "Wizard of Oz" prototype developed in Apple Keynote. The "Wizard of Oz" prototype is an illustration of the full program concept that works only when a human being is generating the responses of the interface. In this way, the prototype interface appears to be functional, even though software programming has not been

completed. The second test, of usability, was used for testing a specific stage of the concept: a collaborative cluster exercise with an Adobe Flash-functioning prototype for testing on the Multitaction multi-touch table.

Method

The team asked four designers to review the Apple Keynote "Wizard of Oz" prototype. These designers represented two small and two large-scale design consultancies. Additionally, two of the participants were interviewed during the initial research phase. Testers were asked to respond to what they saw as the prototype was presented full-screen on the multi-touch Multitaction table provided for the concept development. Each concept test took approximately 1 hour and conversations were audio recorded.

Results

In general, the concept testers responded positively to the concept. The prototype was considered appropriate for small design teams embedded in a large corporate environment, as opposed to widespread adoption across multiple design consultancy teams. The main reason cited for this was the rigid structure of the design process stages presented in the prototype. This structure was effective for training junior design colleagues and for containing the "design mess" in a corporate environment unfamiliar with multi-color post-it notes and paper-covered walls. One participant described the prototype as, potentially, a "good project journal" for documenting the design process and rewinding through the work:

"My job is to be deeply insightful, to create really deep insights and, it's challenging. So you have to work with your information very differently. For me, I'm going back and forth between insights from observations, what's going on at a cultural level, what are the shifts in the industry, and what's a case study. I'm dealing with more types of content than just user observation content and [I'm] working back and forth".

Testers described the tool as a "data organization tool, not a storytelling tool", but the documentation might provide key support to designers in crafting their client stories. For example, one tester wanted to be able to edit insights over time and track the evolution of language or insight focuses. This documentation was another way to capture the evolution of ideas and learning processes, and how they related to data snippets.

Overall, the concept testers were concerned about data retention. The transitions between stages were described as jarring and "anxiety-inducing". Several concept testers gasped at stage changes and complained that the information had "disappeared" and that they wanted some way to review all of the screens at once.

The team was surprised that testers requested the ability to print copies of the digital screens; they wanted to print out what was happening on the table onto paper that they could surround themselves with in a physical space.

“In my gut, after you keep switching [stages], I want to be printing everything out and putting it on the wall. I have to surround myself with the stuff -- because I’m visual, there’s something about it being accessible around me. I wanna see everything at once -- I worry that flipping back and forth would hinder my process. It could be totally silly, but I’ve never worked any other way, so it makes me kinda freaked out not being surrounded by everything”.

Several of the participants admitted to having a visual and spatial memory that was disrupted by the multiple layers of digital staged information. Testers could describe their project room walls, and the distinct screens for each stage seemed to disrupt this memory aid. Testers were also confused by the uncontextualized images and text snippets:

“If I’m reacting to the images, I’m just reacting to them. If I’m trying to put it into the context of a broader story: it could mean something, but maybe it doesn’t. The trouble with still imagery is you don’t know what it’s for. When we know, then we can assign value to it and say that’s important to know. With research, you’re always looking for wonderful examples -- poignant examples of a point you see emerging”.

Not only did the testers want to include meta-data, but they wanted a way to input sketches, diagrams and annotations. One tester specifically requested “football style” drawings that could be made using a stylus or finger.

Analysis

Our concept testers repeatedly compared the concept prototype to their current working model. They are used to surrounding themselves with data by covering the walls with images, snippets, notes and post-its. They were anxious about “disappearing information” and the confusion of their visual memory, which made them disoriented. They also frequently work remotely and would, in several cases, prefer to use the table for individual work, not collaboratively. As a result, the assets of the system had more to do with documentation and having access to the data even if they were not in the same space.

USABILITY TEST

Prototype

To understand how this technology might impact on group dynamics and hierarchy, the team developed Node, a collaborative clustering prototype created in Adobe Flash for use on the multi-touch Multitaction table by groups of designers.

The clustering program in the digital experience allows users to drag, scale, and cluster the pictures. Similar to many software products on the market, it uses standard commercially available touch gestures -- like a two-finger pull & push on the corners of the image to expand and shrink the image and one-finger drag to manipulate photographs.

Clusters are set by stacking images together then pressing and holding on the group of images. The program responds to the user’s touch by drawing a circle around a pile of images. In its final state, the cluster has a large green dot over the images that can then be moved using a one-finger drag.

Method

Twelve graduate design students, divided into four groups of three students each, were recruited from the XXX to participate in two clustering activities for one hour. The teams were comprised of a single senior student in their final year of graduate education at the Illinois Institute of technology (either their second or third year at the university), and two junior students in the first year of their graduate career. Most of the junior participants had no professional or undergraduate design experience.

The teams participated in two sorting exercises: paper clustering (the control) and digital clustering using our Node clustering prototype. Participants were asked to work together to organize images of sport or kitchen products into groups, or “clusters,”. Each team was given a unique content and exercise-order combination in an effort to limit order effects. For the prototype exercises, participants were shown how to zoom, rotate and move the content items with a single or multiple finger touch, how to lock the content together in a cluster with a press-and-hold gesture and were cautioned that clusters could only be made by one participant because of programming limitations.

The activities’ audio and visuals were documented using an aerial video camera and a secondary camera at one edge of the table. The team recorded observations throughout the two testing activities and a single team member served as activity moderator and trainer for all of the team’s testing. On completion of the second activity, participants were interviewed individually by a team researcher who asked the following questions:

1. Tell us about how easy/hard you found the activity.
2. Describe how you participated in the activity.
3. What would you change?
4. What would happen if you tried to use this table in your design work?
5. How do you think it might help you? How do you think it might hinder you?
6. What would you be frustrated with?

General Observations

The research team analyzed the paper and digital exercises in addition to the comments made in the individual interviews conducted after the group exercises. In general, we noted two roles: leaders, or senior members, and followers, or junior members. While participants were selected to amplify the dichotomy of junior and senior participants, the selected senior participants were not always the table leaders.

Forming Consensus in Both Activities

Regardless of the medium used in the activities, two types of leadership style were observed. The first style of leadership observed could be characterized as “command and control”. Junior members would start a discussion by throwing out ideas about how to cluster while the senior member would judge, strike down ideas and choose other strategies. In one test, a junior member suggested clustering the images by color and a senior member remarked, “[That] doesn’t make sense ... clearly this is content related”. As a result, the team proceeded to cluster by sport, coming up with 20 categories of data for 45 images.

The second type of leader exhibited facilitation and iteration behaviors. Users would start to cluster images together and if the team felt that images fell outside their initial construct, a single participant would stop, announce the problem, and suggest new ways of grouping images together.

Paper Cluster Exercise - Body Language and Leadership

In the paper clustering exercises participants were able to control the conversation by singling out specific pieces of data through physical gestures, pulling the data out of the second dimension and bringing it into the third dimension above the

rest of the data (Figure 3). In one case, a participant picked up an image above the table, held it up for the others to see and asked, “What is this? Where do we put it?” This grabbed the attention of the other group members, physically separated them from what they were doing, allowing them to help her and quickly reach consensus.

Paper Clustering Exercise - Team Flow

We also observed a team clear the table by picking up groups of data and shuffling them by hand, creating clear space on the table (Figure 4). This enabled them to create “thinking space” or a blank slate to help them sort the data, but it also created a personal and group data divide where the group could focus and have a conversation together based on the images on the table.

Finally, we saw that group members had subtle ways of communicating with each other during the physical exercise. For example, when one participant held a photograph in his hands for a long period of time, another participant would lean over or walk around the table to provide assistance in figuring out how it might be grouped. This naturally instigated a conversation about where to put the information and built consensus about group definitions.

Figure 3: Participants showing information to drive the conversation.

Figure 4: Participants collecting data into individual working stacks.

Digital Clustering Exercise - Contrasts in Leadership

However, in the digital exercise, users had to employ deliberate actions and assert conversational dominance. This was done by enlarging images on the screen to draw people's attention to them and controlling data access and the largest screen area (Figure 5). Junior members could no longer see the images that they were working with and were forced to focus on the enlarged image. Furthermore, we also observed senior leaders use motion to direct the attention of their junior members: leaders would touch and shake images to direct a conversation towards that specific image.

Digital Clustering Exercise - Contrasts in Team Flow

Overall, we saw that users were challenged to form consensus in the digital experience as easily as in the physical exercise. Participants were observed talking less about the data because team members were engaged in their specific activity of creating a digital cluster (Figure 6). Participants described the digital experience as "so engrossing and entertaining" but that it was hard to focus on what other group members were doing. Participants also struggled to communicate with each other non-verbally. Because of the singular participant focus, few participants made eye contact with each other and they kept

their heads down, focusing on the table and rarely looking up from the screen. Most activity took place on the table: conversations about the data, asserting conversational focus on a particular image, and gathering one's own data for the cluster.

Because of the overall reduction in group conversation and strong focus on individual actions, participants tended to move images that they didn't know what to do with into the center with no comments or pause. As a result, participants were challenged at the end to figure out what they should do next.

Unintended Digital Disruptions & Affordances

We also noted how the prototype's technical execution interfered with the ability of an individual to accomplish their own cluster activity. The team observed "data crashes" where participants dragged information across the table and accidentally crossed paths with another participant. Because every touched piece is brought to the front, if two participants cross information at the same time, one of them would lose the touch input and only one image would follow the intended trajectory. The other image would be "dropped" and left on the table where it was lost in the crash. Because this disrupted the intended flow, they would lose focus and move on.

Figure 5: Senior participant controlling a table conversation by enlarging content

Figure 6: Participants working individually with their heads down.

The technology also interfered with social dynamics. For the setup of the test, a double tap touch brought up the menu that retrieved the image dataset and displayed it on the table. If a team participant accidentally triggered the menu and selected a menu item, more images would be loaded onto the table, covering most, if not all, of the work completed by the team. This action was always irreversible, meaning the data had to be dealt with and could not be removed easily.

Though the research team did not intentionally plan this action, several teams triggered more data, producing surprising findings. If a team member accidentally hit the menu button and “spilled data onto the table” the group would blame the participant and make him or her liable for “cleaning up the mess”.

DISCUSSION

Social Behavior

Even though the participants in the study are heavy digital device users (smartphones, tablets, etc.), the Multi-taction table was still perceived as a single person’s device. One participant specifically asked “who’s going to control [the multi-touch table]?” inferring that only one person could move images at a time. Furthermore, in the subsequent interviews, most participants described using the device for their own personal use and not for collaborative work. According to one participant:

“If you’re working with just one surface, it feels like that one surface is yours. It’s almost disconcerting to have multiple hands on it. I think people have this one terminal, one person kind of viewpoint on things, which I think is left over from personal computing days”.

The team suggests that this might be because the prototype did not deliver an exceptional experience comparable to working with paper, or that the functional portion of the prototype shown did not have enough features to warrant the abandonment of paper. As researchers, we made the choice of having the images appear in a randomized way in order to balance the positioning of people around the table and create an egalitarian multi-user workspace.

Communication

The digital prototype was not able to facilitate natural group behavior and communication. It did not allow for eye contact between team members or for team members to seamlessly accomplish their own tasks and clusters. Because the digital prototype engages so much of the participant’s attention, the prototype became the focal point of activity and made it easy for participants to ignore the movements and behaviors of others. For this reason, conversational and behavioral leadership in the digital experience depended on deliberate and intentional actions. This included actions like enlarging photographs so that no other participant could look at any other image, or pointing and moving an image to gain attention and input.

Participants may have rejected the device for collaboration because physical space and reach dictated what they were capable of doing, and participants controlled the actions of others, restricting access to photographs by collecting all of the images on their side of the table.

Ludic Behavior

Because of the entertainment value of such a large touchscreen device, several participants “played” with it before beginning the task that was assigned to them. Fun can help break the technology barrier but it will significantly raise the users’ feature expectations as they compare their personal tablet experiences to working on the table, rather than focusing on the assigned task.

This might be an artifact of the learning process: users will understand the functions of the table better after they have explored it: testing the boundaries of what is possible and what is not. During the first minutes of each test, participants tried different gestures and tested the physics rules (i.e., participants tried to use inertia to send a picture in a given direction). It is difficult to ascertain whether the differences between physical and digital clustering come from the fact that the participants were interacting with the table for the first time but were more familiar with the clustering exercise, or if the digital experience had less to offer in terms of possibilities and thus lowered the efficiency of a work group.

Paper vs Digital: The Emotional Experience

The two different tests revealed different emotional responses on the part of participants. The paper prototype created direct communication when someone showed a picture in order to catch others’ attention or gestured by holding a piece of paper up for a long time to indicate they needed help. Both behaviors might be common in other practices and were easily understood by others.

In contrast, the levels of interaction with the digital surface when participants required attention or help involved moving the images about and changing their size. This activity had to be repeated multiple times before the other participants became aware of the problem. These interactions occurred on a trial and error basis, especially at the beginning of the activity when the way to manipulate the information was still not clear for some participants.

Concerning the digital disruptions caused by accidents with the menu, the emotional response was to blame the participant who had made the mistake instead of blaming the technology or even the group of designers who were present during the test. We observed that participants with a fast learning curve concerning the features and affordances of the interface were less tolerant of this kind of problem.

It is not our intention to generalize these situations, but at least in relation to this test it is possible to connect the different levels of learning about the interface with different emotional experiences concerning the roles of authority and tolerance

shown towards other participants who were less skilled at using digital devices. The recognition of a digital system as a tool, and not as a medium or as a facilitator, creates levels of expertise that can affect the role of the participants in a positive or negative way.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Concept Direction

From a user-centered point of view, the team would like to expand our concept of a workspace to include a team journal, where users could see their information and scrub from the past to the present. Because the concept prototype was presented as a number of discrete screens, users were concerned about “where their data went”.

We envisage the concept as moving towards the creation of a network of team digital devices with the table interface as a single node or touchpoint. Rather than force users to be co-located, the concept will explore how the table might bring together a centrally-located group around the table, as well as involve those who are located at a distance. This would allow users to use their own personal devices such as laptops, tablets, and smartphones -- key components of how they access and accomplish “work”.

Participants also wanted to add layers of other information, so future iterations should enable users to sketch and draw on top of the images and add “drawn” files. We imagine the addition of the third dimension could further replicate the tangible experience of working with physical materials, and make it possible for users to zoom in and out of the workspace and data snippets and be more seamless to navigate.

Research Recommendations

For further research, we would like to investigate how our concept could be an active participant, rather than a work tool. This might help shift blame towards the technology rather than social relationships, which can be frail and easily broken.

As a social tool, the table could help moderate and facilitate conversation, encouraging quiet users to speak up, and instructing all users on the specific activity, ultimately promoting individual engagement in the group context.

Finally, the team would also like to explore the table orientation by designing the screen to have a top and a bottom when posted on a vertical surface. This would further mimic the vertical space paradigm currently in use. This orientation could promote eye contact between individuals and the ability for participants to read other non-verbal communication.

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